

Inter-code Comparison of Time Independent Pulsed Sphere Benchmark Results

By
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The pulsed sphere benchmark problems are a set of physical experiments that have been used to verify Monte Carlo codes and evaluate nuclear data. All Monte Carlo codes rely on benchmark experiments that test the features of the code to verify that the simulations are producing realistic results. In the case of time dependent codes, which simulate the entire problem over progressive time steps instead of transporting particles independently, benchmark problems that produce results of a time dependent nature are required. The pulsed sphere problems use time binned tallies to measure the time-of-flight of the neutrons, but they can also be run in time independent fashion with methods explained in this thesis. The results from simulations can be compared with experiment data to demonstrate the capability of the codes to simulate the problems. Existing inputs for the pulsed spheres in the Monte Carlo codes MCNP and Mercury were run in time independent mode to produce a set of results for comparisons. The purpose of the research was to run the problems for the first time in the Monte Carlo code Shift in order to demonstrate that the code can produce reasonable results. The pulsed spheres were modeled and simulated in a time independent version of Shift in preparation for the potential use of these problems to verify a time dependent version of Shift as well as other time dependent Monte Carlo codes. Shift results from multiple materials in the set of pulsed sphere experiments agreed with experiment data as well as the other codes, which shows that Shift can produce reasonable results, and the time dependent version of Shift can be tested. An in-development time dependent version of Shift was also obtained, and preliminary results show that the code is also capable of simulating the pulsed spheres.

Key Words: Shift, Monte Carlo, benchmarks

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1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Benchmark problems are essential for the verification of Monte Carlo neutron transport codes. There are several possible sources of error in these codes such as modeling approximations, coding mistakes, and uncertainties in numbers such as cross sections. It is important that the results from simulations approximate the data from physical experiments to a reasonable small degree of error to verify that the codes are producing results that are predictive of reality. The selection of benchmark problems is dependent on the range of features that need to be verified. These problems need to be simple enough in order to reduce extraneous sources of error [1].

The Center for Exascale Monte-Carlo Neutron Transport (CEMeNT) is a Predictive Science Academic Alliance Program (PSAAP-III) focused investigatory center. One of the primary goals of the center is to advance Monte Carlo neutron transport capabilities for time dependent problems. Time dependent simulations are significantly more complicated than time independent problems and require additional algorithmic features including keeping track of particle data after each time step. In order to verify the results of developing codes which are incorporating time dependent capabilities, an appropriate benchmark problem must be selected that can exercise these additional features. The pulsed sphere benchmark problems are a set of experiments performed at Lawrence Livermore National Lab (LLNL) during the

1960s-1980s which have been used for verifying neutron transport codes as well as evaluating neutron cross section libraries [2][3]. These benchmark problems are ideal because they have relatively simple geometries and material specifications, are well documented, and incorporate results of a time dependent nature [4]. The goal of this thesis is to demonstrate the capability of the Monte Carlo code Shift to simulate the pulsed sphere problems.

1.2 Problem Description

The pulsed sphere experiments have a relatively simple geometric design. A pulse of high energy neutrons are emitted from the center of a small sphere of material. The neutrons can interact with the sphere of material before traveling outwards towards a detector. The four main components of the design are the target apparatus used for creating the pulse of neutrons, the sphere of material, the surrounding structure and beamline assemblies, and the detector itself. A simplified version of the setup is shown in figure 5.

1.2.1 Neutron Source

The neutron source is created through the $T(d, n)^4He$ reaction which creates high energy neutrons of about 14 MeV. A beam of 400 keV deuterons is directed at a tritium-laced titanium target. The target reaction is not simulated in any of the neutron transport codes; however, there are several characteristics of the neutron

source that are important to capture when implementing these problems in the various transport codes. The neutron source intensity does have a small angular dependence. The angle is calculated from the direction of the incoming deuteron beam and is fixed with respect to the geometry of the target assembly regardless of whether the deuteron beam is actually simulated. The source energy distribution also varies with the emission direction of the source particle. Both of these distributions are shown in figures 1 and 2 respectively. The neutron energy can reach over 15 MeV in the direction of the beam at 0 degrees and just under 13 MeV in the opposite direction. The assembly itself is made out of various metals such as tungsten and aluminum. It is designed to have a minimal effect on the emitted neutrons, but it is important to incorporate it into the simulations. The deuteron beam is used to create a short pulse of neutrons with a full width half maximum (FWHM) between 2 to 10 nanoseconds, depending on the experiment.

Figure 1: Angular distribution of neutrons [1].

Figure 2: Angularly dependent energy distribution of neutrons [5].

Figure 3: Geometry of the target assembly [1].

1.2.2 Sphere

The spherical portion of these test problems are the spheres of material surrounding the target apparatus. These spheres have a hollow conical section which fits the target apparatus, but this section is not between the source and the detector and has little effect on the results. A wide range of materials and sphere sizes were used in the experiments. Materials include lithium, carbon, beryllium, concrete, water, nitrogen, iron, lead, uranium, and plutonium as well as many others. The radius of the spheres ranged from 0.5 to 5 mean free paths (mfp). Additionally, the liquid and radioactive spheres had a thin outer shell made of a metal such as stainless steel to hold the material or make it safer for handling. The geometry of one of the spheres is shown

in figure 4.

Figure 4: Example geometry of a 2.9 mfp carbon sphere [1]

1.2.3 Structure

The spheres were placed in a large pit with concrete walls. The pit floor is made of aluminum to reduce scattering of the neutrons. An important factor was the distance to the walls being much larger distance than the radii of the spheres. Iron and borated paraffin collimators were placed in holes in the walls which shielded the detectors from background radiation from the pit. Three primary beamlines were used for the experiments. Low energy measurements were taken at an angle of 26 degrees from the deuteron beam while higher energy measurements were taken at the

30 and 120 degree beamlines. The 30 degree beamline is actually at about 38.8877 degrees with respect to the deuteron beam while the 120 degree beamline is about 116.7053 degrees. The notation of 30 and 120 degrees is due to the angles being measured with respect to the 26 degree beamline. A simplified overview of the setup is shown in figure 5. The pit and collimators are filled with air. The air has relatively little effect on the neutron spectrum but is typically included in the models. In many cases, the concrete beamlines could be modeled as black absorbers since reflection off the concrete was negligible [6].

Figure 5: Simplified not-to-scale geometry of the setup [5].

1.2.4 Detector

The detector is situated in a separate room at the end of one of the beamlines. Two main types of detectors were used in the experiments which measured neutrons from about 2 to 15 MeV. Either NE213 or Pilot B cylindrical scintillators with length and diameter of 5.08 cm were used, depending on the experiment. In some cases, a stilbene detector was used, but none of those experiments were included as comparisons in this research. Each detector has its own efficiency curve over the range of neutron energies measured. The most common detector was an NE213-A detector with a ^{22}Na bias of 1.6 MeV. That efficiency curve is shown in figure 6. The response of the detector is well documented and can be implemented into neutron transport codes as a tally modifier.

The most important measurement from these experiments is the time of flight (TOF) of the neutrons. Accordingly, the experimental detector setup measured the neutrons in time bins with a width of 2 nanoseconds. Since the time of flight of the neutrons is dependent on the energy of the neutron and the distance traveled, the distance from the center of the sphere to the detector is an important characteristic of the experiments. The direct flight path distance to the detector ranged from around 700 to 1000 cm. The distance to the detector compared to its size is so dramatic that the detector covers a relatively tiny solid angle and the detailed geometry of the detector is rarely built into the transport models due to an extreme number of histories needed to obtain sufficiently small statistical uncertainty on the detector

response. There are several methods used to improve the effectiveness of tallies without degrading the results which will be discussed later in the Methods section of this thesis.

Figure 6: NE213 Detector efficiency with a bias of 1.6 MeV [1].

1.2.5 Experiment Results

The primary result that is of interest for these problems is the time of flight spectrum recorded by the detector in the experiments. There is data available for the energy spectra of neutrons that reached the detector; however, all this data is calculated from the time of flight data and not measured directly. An example is shown for a 2.9 mfp carbon sphere with a direct flight path of 766 cm. There are several important features of the TOF tallies. There is a peak at the lowest detected time

which corresponds to the bulk of the neutrons which traveled through the material without colliding. This is followed by a lower energy spectrum of scattered neutrons that is highly dependent on the sphere of material being used. Several of the spheres incorporate fissile material such as uranium-235 which also adds a small amount of fission neutrons to the spectrum. The time of flight spectrum is useful because it can be used to assess the impact of scattering and absorption cross sections as well as the codes used to simulate these mechanics. In the case of time dependent codes, the ability to keep track of neutrons over multiple time steps and still register the correct distribution as a function of time will be tested.

Figure 7: Experiment Time of Flight Tally for a 2.9 mfp carbon sphere with a 766 cm flight path [1].

1.3 Background Literature

The Pulsed Sphere experiments were designed with the intention that they could be used to validate Monte Carlo codes and evaluate cross section data. In the past, these experiments have been used to validate Monte Carlo codes such as TART [5, 7], MCNP [4], and more recently Mercury [8]. The more recent Mercury simulations in 2010 focused on understanding the differences induced by different nuclear data libraries. The best comparisons of the results from the pulsed sphere problems computed from several transport codes requires that they all use the same nuclear data libraries.

A study performed in 2017 examined the sensitivity of the results to computational choices and changes in parameters that were improperly documented [9]. One example was the lack of information about the length of the flight path. The flight path to the detector was specified, but it was unknown whether the distance was taken to the front, middle, or end of the detector. Other analysis was performed for different nuclear data libraries, slightly modified detector angles, the presence of the concrete beamlines, and uncertainties in the neutron source. The flight path and detector angle uncertainties had a negligible effect on the results, but the nuclear data libraries again caused significant discrepancies. The simplified geometry of using concrete beamlines that act as black absorbers was found to be sufficiently accurate such that a detailed setup of the entire experiment pit was unnecessary. One conclusion relevant to the results collected in this research is the incorrectly modeled neutron source. A number

of neutrons around 2.8 MeV are released from dueteron-deuteron interactions near the center of the sphere. These neutrons are not present in MCNP because the deuterons are not explicitly simulated. The consequence of the source error is that results are less reliable below neutron energies of 4 MeV.

Another more recent simulation of the pulsed spheres was performed with the MAVRIC/Monaco and TRIPOLI-4 codes [10]. While the paper also explores various nuclear data libraries, the relevant piece of information for using Shift is the type of detector used. Similarly to Shift, these codes did not have the point detector diagnostic particle capabilities like MCNP and Mercury. Their solution was to model the detector as a volumetric region in the geometry. The volume they used was a segment of a spherical shell, and this approach was implemented into the Shift models that are included in this thesis. The results from using this alternative detector were still very accurate which improves the confidence in the methodology used in Shift.

2 Methodology

2.1 Simulations and Hardware

The bulk of this thesis focuses on time independent simulations of the pulsed sphere problems using the Monte Carlo codes MCNP, Mercury, and Shift. A time independent simulation involves transporting batches of particles until the end of the life of the particles. A time dependent dynamic simulation is very similar, except it transports all simulation particles across a single timestep before moving any particles through the next time step. If a particle is still alive at the end of the timestep, it must be put into census and stored in memory. Although the ultimate goal is to use the pulsed sphere problems to validate time dependent codes such as Shift, running the problems in time independent mode is important to demonstrate that simulated results are accurate and that the problems can be properly simulated using any particular neutron transport tool. If a code has not been shown to produce accurate results with a static calculation, incorrect results from a dynamic calculation are more difficult to understand. Running a time based problem in time independent mode can be made possible in two ways. Many codes can run a static calculation while keeping track of how long each particle would have been alive. This allows codes like MCNP and Mercury to have time based tallies without iterating over time steps. For codes that do not have the capability to keep track of the time of flight of the neutrons such as Shift, an energy tally can be simulated instead. This energy tally can be directly

compared to energy tallies produced by other time independent codes, but it can also be converted into time bins based on the same calculation used to convert the experiment data into energy bins. This calculation is an approximation and is discussed in more detail in section 2.2.3. Because the calculation is an approximation, the best comparisons are with time of flight data.

All time independent simulations were performed on CPU-based versions of MCNP, Mercury, and Shift. The time dependent simulations also used CPU-based versions of Shift and Mercury. A GPU-based version of Mercury exists, and a GPU-based version of Shift is in development, but only CPU-based codes were used for simulations. The MCNP simulations utilized the high performance computing cluster (Rogue) located at Oregon State University (OSU). Mercury and Shift were primarily executed on the Lassen supercomputing cluster at Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory (LLNL).

2.2 Codes

2.2.1 MCNP

MCNP is a very commonly used Monte Carlo code developed by Los Alamos National Laboratory (LANL). It is the most used and thoroughly tested code, so comparisons with MCNP are useful for verification purposes. Existing input files for eleven of the pulsed sphere problems are included in the MCNP Shielding Validation Suite. These input files are relatively thorough in describing the relevant geometry, and materials. They include the geometry for all three beamline assemblies although only one is

used in the default files. The collimators on the beamlines are designed to isolate the detector from sources of particles other than from the sphere. The MCNP files do not model the collimators in detail, so black absorbers that have the particle importance set to zero are used under the assumption that negligible amounts of neutrons that reach those locations will reach the detector. Using black absorbers in the model is a close approximation of the effects of the collimators [9]. The experiment pit is not modeled, and to accommodate the ring detector, the beamlines are extended from cylinders into cones. This model was shown to be acceptable by the IAEA [9]. Without modification, ten of the files are based on experiments that use the 30 degree beamline with an NE213 detector response function while the concrete input uses the 120 degree beamline. Important characteristics such as pulse width, flight path, beamline, and detector for the other experiments with the same material are listed but not built into the files. These files include both time and energy binned tallies designed to replicate the same bins as the experiment data. One important feature of these files is the f5 ring detector used for variance reduction. In MCNP, the f5 tally uses a next event estimator to reduce the number of particles needed for accurate results for point detectors or ring detectors. The ring detector is equivalent to a point detector, but it takes advantage of the symmetry of the problem. The ring is set so that all points on the ring are at the correct distance from the center of the sphere and at the correct angle from the target deuteron beam.

2.2.2 Mercury

Mercury is a next generation general purpose Monte Carlo code developed by LLNL. Unlike MCNP, Mercury has the capability to run in time dependent mode. While time independent simulations are the focus of this work, the capability for running the pulsed sphere problems in time dependent mode will be important for future continuations of this research. Time independent runs of Mercury are just time dependent runs with a single time step. Existing input files written by Richard "Spike" Procassini for a wide variety of the experiments were provided by the Mercury team. One potential impediment towards comparisons was the limited overlap between the experiments being modeled in the provided input files for MCNP and Mercury. There are many slight variations for each material, and most of the experiments represented in the MCNP set were not included in the larger Mercury set. For example, the uranium-235 file in MCNP was a 0.7 mfp sphere using the 30 degree beamline with the detector at 766 cm while the multiple Mercury files were based on the 26 degree beamline with a much longer flight path. This could be remedied by manually modifying input files to create matching simulations. The Mercury input files use a point detector tally with ray trace diagnostic particles. This serves a similar purpose to the MCNP ring detector. The geometry and materials in the Mercury input files are very similar to MCNP. The walls of the pit are modeled in the Mercury files unlike in the MCNP files where just the collimators are modeled. The collimators are designed to eliminate particles coming from directions other than the sphere, so the

walls should have a negligible effect on the tallies. A significant effort was made to run Mercury with matching nuclear data. Previous versions of the pulsed spheres had run Mercury on the ENDL, JEFF, and ENDF nuclear data sets, but both MCNP and Shift used the more recent ENDF/B-VII.1 library which was not available through Mercury. Scott McKinley and other staff at LLNL helped to establish a version of ENDF/B-VII.1 that could be run with Mercury, so all codes ran with the same data.

2.2.3 Shift

Shift is a massively parallel neutron transport code developed by Oak Ridge National Library (ORNL). A time dependent version of Shift is under development at CEMeNT, so performing comparisons with the time independent version of Shift is valuable. Shift was chosen by CEMeNT because the code performs extremely well at exascale and was available to be developed further. It had the best characteristics out of codes where time dependent modes could be implemented. No input files for the pulsed sphere benchmark problems exist in Shift, and two methods were taken to build proper input decks. A build of Shift coupled to the Lava library from ORNL is capable of taking MCNP input files and converting most of it into the Shift input format. During the time it took to obtain a build of Shift with those capabilities, input files were written from scratch in the native Geometria (GG) language present in Shift. The primary obstacle for performing time of flight simulations in both cases is that Shift does not have time binned tallies. All results from Shift are energy binned

tallies. These tallies can be compared to energy tallies in other codes or converted into time bins using the relativistic first flight approximation in equation 1. This equation assumes that the neutrons travel in a straight line from the center of the sphere to the detector at the final energy of the neutron. Assuming that all collisions happen at the center of the sphere is a reasonable assumption in most cases since the flight path is typically several hundred times longer than the radius of the sphere where most of the collisions take place.

$$E = rme * \left(\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - ((fp)^2 / (t^2 * c^2))}} \right) - 1 \right) \quad (1)$$

In this equation, E is the energy of the neutron [MeV], rme is the rest mass energy of the neutron [MeV], fp is the length of the flight path to the detector [cm], t is the time of flight [ns], and c is the speed of light [cm/ns].

The Lava library coupled build of Shift does not convert the entire MCNP input file into Shift. The geometry, source, and materials are translated, however the physics solver block and the tallies are not. This presents an additional problem, because Shift does not have the next event estimator tallies like MCNP. A volumetric cell tally of the flux is required, and any volumetric cell that approximates the experimental detector would be extremely unlikely to detect each source particle due to the tiny solid angle covered by the detector. Using a detector with the approximate dimensions of the experimental detector requires a huge number of particles to reach reasonable uncertainties. In order to reduce the computation cost of reaching simi-

lar uncertainties as the other codes, the detector was expanded into a ring. A shell segment formed between two spherical and two planar surfaces was used to model a volumetric ring with the approximate width and depth of the experimental detector. This detector takes advantage of the symmetry of the problem since the source and geometry only vary with respect to the polar angle from the detector.

Input files using the Geometria language for a couple spheres were built from scratch. Combinatorial geometry was used with the MCNP geometry as a template. The Geometria language does not have as much documentation as input file languages in other codes, so the direct translation of the combinatorial geometry was difficult. The sphere itself was included, but the concrete beamline assemblies as well as the complicated target assembly were not included before work was directed towards running the more accurate Lava library coupled version of Shift. The target assembly in figure 3 only contained about 0.082cm of material in the direction of the detectors, so it would only have a minor effect on the tallies. A larger problem was the lack of parameters needed to model the source. The source in the pulsed spheres includes an angularly dependent energy distribution. The source in the MCNP input files breaks the possible directions into 21 separate angles and gives each segment its own energy distribution. In the Geometria language, the source could not be described with that level of detail. Only a single energy distribution could be implemented, so the distribution for the segment in MCNP that contained the direct path to the detector was chosen. This does not adequately measure the neutrons that originate

in other segments then scatter into the detector. . Comparisons with Shift should be done with the Lava library coupled build since it is a more complete model to compare with experiment data or other codes.

2.2.4 Time Dependence

Both Mercury and Shift can be run in time dependent mode. In Mercury, only three changes needed to be made to run a time dependent simulation of the existing pulsed sphere files. In the input file, the mode was changed from static to dynamic, a time step and end time was specified, and variable weight needed to be toggled on. Shift did not have a time dependent version at the start of this research, however, Aaron Reynolds at CEMeNT has built a time dependent version of the code on which the pulsed spheres can be tested. The current time dependent build of Shift is relatively untested, and one of the goals of this research is to eventually use results from the pulsed spheres to ensure that the code is running accurately. The Lava library has not yet been coupled with the code, so the MCNP input files cannot be used to run the pulsed spheres. A Geometria input file was used to produce results, and future work could include implementing the Lava library for additional accuracy.

In both Mercury and Shift, the time step was set to two nanoseconds. The current build of Shift is designed to take a tally at each time step, so the choice of two nanoseconds ensures that Shift is replicating the experiment data. The Mercury files did not take a tally at every time step. Since the Mercury files used ray trace

diagnostic particles, a tally over each time step does not produce accurate results. Ray trace diagnostic particles are transported until the end of the particle's life during the time step the code is at regardless of whether or not that would take longer than the step itself. Mercury still transported the standard transport particles in a time dependent manner, but the tally results incorporate the time independent methods. Turning off the diagnostic particles and adding a detector to tally the results from the transport particles would provide a more interesting result to compare time dependent results with.

3 Results and Analysis

3.1 Results

3.1.1 MCNP

All eleven input files included in the MCNP Shielding Validation Suite were run with 10^7 histories and compared with experiment data included with the distribution. For brevity, only results for carbon and iron spheres are presented here in detail. These materials were chosen to show results across a wide range of atomic numbers. Figure 8 shows the results from a 2.9 mfp carbon sphere with a 4 ns pulse width, an NE213 detector with 1.6 MeV bias, and a flight path of 766 cm along the 30 degree beamline. These input files have been documented before,

Figure 8: MCNP results for a carbon 2.9 mfp sphere with 10^7 histories.

Figure 9: MCNP results for an iron 0.9 mfp sphere with 10^7 histories.

Since the energy bins in Shift must be converted to time bins using the first flight approximation in equation 1, it would be useful to determine the accuracy of the approximation. The MCNP input files contained both time and energy tallies, so the energy tally could be converted and compared with the standard time tally from the same simulation. The results from a simulation of a carbon sphere are shown in figure 10. While there are minor differences in the spectrum of scattered neutrons, the approximation fits the time binned data relatively well. This approximation should not introduce levels of error that would prevent converted energy binned tallies from Shift from being compared with other codes.

Figure 10: Time binned (MCNP) vs converted energy binned (MCNP FF) tallies for a carbon 2.9 mfp sphere with 10^7 histories.

Another change made to the model in Shift is the cell detector. MCNP and Mercury used point/ring detector "next event estimators" to calculate the tally results, but Shift is limited to a tally over a volumetric cell. As described in the methods section, this cell was modeled in a ring to replicate the MCNP ring detector which takes advantage of the symmetry of the problem. If the cell is too wide, it will capture neutrons at a greater range of angles than the experiment setup or other codes. In order to ensure the validity of this cell tally, the same geometry and tally were built into MCNP. The results in figure 11 show that this cell tally is virtually indistinguishable from the ring detector. This tallying method should produce accurate results in Shift.

Figure 11: F5 "next event estimator" ring detector vs F4 cell tally for a 0.9 mfp iron sphere with 10^7 histories.

3.1.2 Mercury

The Mercury input files were written more recently than the MCNP input files and strived to add some minor improvements to the simulation. In particular, the experiment pit and beamline assemblies were modeled in more detail. Although Mercury was chosen for its time dependent capabilities, time independent results from Mercury are important for ensuring that the The results from Mercury are also useful for providing another comparison for the Shift results. Figures 12 and 13 show the results from Mercury compared with the experiment data.

Figure 12: Mercury results for a 0.9 mfp Iron sphere with 10^7 histories.

Figure 13: Mercury results for a 0.7 mfp U-235 sphere with 10^7 histories.

3.1.3 Shift and Comparisons

The Shift output gave an error when transporting the particles. When running spheres that included isotope manganese-55, the code reported an error with the scattering and absorption cross sections failing to sum to the total cross section. This isotope was only present in small amounts, and the cross section summation error was only about five percent depending on the energy of the neutron. When Mercury was run with the ENDF/B-VII.1 data, it ran into a similar issue. A reaction called the "sum of remaining reactions" which is typically reserved for neutrons above 20 MeV was used for this particular interaction with neutrons from 12 to 15 MeV. This had a negligible effect on the results, but could indicate an error with the ENDF/B-VII.1 library or how the codes are using it.

Due to Shift requiring a volumetric cell tally instead of diagnostic particle point/ring detectors, significantly more particles were used to produce accurate results. Since Shift records its tallies in energy bins, direct comparisons to the energy binned results from other codes are the best way to compare results. Energy binned results from both MCNP and Shift are shown in figures 14 and 15. The experiment data was only captured in time bins, so there are no direct comparisons to energy data from the experiments.

Figure 14: Energy binned results for a 0.9 mfp iron sphere with 10^9 histories in Shift and 10^7 histories in MCNP.

Figure 15: Energy binned results for a 2.9 mfp carbon sphere with 10^9 histories in Shift and 10^7 histories in MCNP.

The results from Shift are very close to MCNP. Both simulations used the same geometry, source, tallying methods, data library, and other aspects of the MCNP input files. The only major difference should be the transporter code itself. These problems have never been run on the Shift code before, and these results show that Shift can produce reasonable pulsed sphere results.

Time binned results are also interesting to compare with even though they can only be produced from Shift using the first flight approximation. Figures 16 and 17 compare the experiment data to Shift results.

Figure 16: Shift results for a 0.9 mfp iron sphere with 10^9 histories.

Figure 17: Shift results for a 2.9 mfp carbon sphere with 10^9 histories.

Particularly with the carbon sphere where more scattering takes place, there are some small but noticeable differences. As seen in Figure 10, the first flight approximation is responsible for some of the more pronounced differences. The Shift results are still nearly identical to MCNP, and the approximation is still relatively accurate, especially where there were fewer pronounced scattering features.

The Shift input files written with the Geometria language were also run. Figure 18 shows the energy binned results compared with MCNP and the Lava library coupled build of Shift, and figure 19 shows the time binned results of both versions of Shift using the first flight approximation.

Figure 18: Shift Lava vs. Geometria energy binned results for a 0.9 mfp iron sphere with 10^9 histories compared with MCNP energy binned results with 10^7 histories.

Figure 19: Shift Lava vs. Geometria converted to time bins for a 0.9 mfp iron sphere with 10^9 histories

The Geometria files are not as accurate as the Lava library coupled build. There are noticeable features in the scattered spectrum that differ from the other simulations and experiment data. These results have the same general shape and can still function as a useful comparison for the time dependent build of Shift which does not yet have Lava library compatibility.

Results from all three codes were compared to data from experiments. Figure 20 graphs the time of flight results for the 0.9 mfp iron sphere. It is difficult to tell the difference between the codes, so figure 21 compares their differences from the experiment data. The simulated results were divided by the experiment results to calculate the ratio which was plotted on the same time scale.

Figure 20: Results for a 0.9 mfp iron sphere with 10^9 histories in Shift and 10^7 histories in MCNP and Mercury.

Figure 21: The ratio of simulated tallies over experiment results for a 0.9 mfp iron sphere.

MCNP and Shift had relatively similar results. Shift took the majority of its input from MCNP, so this is expected. The main difference occurred in the 150-250 ns range where Shift had a more pronounced valley and peak, but this is due to the first flight approximation, and the difference was very minor. The input files for Mercury were supposed to add some minor improvements, and overall, it was slightly closer to the experiment data.

3.1.4 Time Dependent Results

A time dependent and time independent simulation of a 0.9 mfp iron sphere was performed with Mercury. As expected, the two versions were nearly identical which could be due to the time dependent simulation incorporating diagnostic particles that ignore the census at the end of each time step.

Figure 22: Time independent vs. time dependent Mercury results for a 0.9 mfp iron sphere with 10^7 histories.

A time dependent simulation was also ran with the new CPU based version of Shift. Since the current dynamic build of Shift does is not coupled with the Lava library, the Geometria files were run instead. The fact that the time independent version of Shift does not produce time binned results presents another complication. In order to compare the dynamic simulation to the static simulation of Shift, the first flight approximation must be used. Figure 23 contains the preliminary time dependent results.

Figure 23: Time independent vs. time dependent Shift Geometria results for a 0.9 mfp iron sphere with 10^9 histories.

The early results are promising. The time dependent tallies are relatively close to the time independent tallies. Although more detailed analysis will be done with the more accurate Shift simulations when that becomes available, this shows that the new time dependent version of Shift can produce reasonable results.

4 Conclusion

The goal of this thesis was to demonstrate for the first time that Shift has the capability to simulate the pulsed sphere benchmark problems. The pulsed sphere benchmark problems are a useful set of experiments for evaluating cross section data and verifying Monte Carlo neutron transport codes. Comparisons between codes and experiment data can identify simulation errors in the modeling, the data libraries used, and the codes themselves. Simulations of the pulsed spheres in MCNP and Mercury have been done in the past, and were performed again in this work to examine the differences between the models and provide references for the novel simulations performed in Shift. Shift was run in time independent mode using a portion of the MCNP pulsed sphere input. Although there were several limitations to tallies in Shift, a very close approximation of the time of flight tallies was produced. The time independent results compare very well with MCNP and the experiment data. Now that the capability of Shift to run the pulsed spheres has been demonstrated, future versions of Shift can use the pulsed sphere problems to validate time dependent features. Preliminary time dependent results using a novel time dependent build of Shift are promising. At this stage, less accurate models had to be used, however, future implementations of Shift can perform more detailed simulations soon. The results of this work show that the pulsed sphere benchmark problems can be used for the verification of time dependent Monte Carlo codes in the future.

5 Future Work

The primary focus of future research will be on the verification of time dependent codes such as Shift. A version of the time dependent build of Shift coupled with the Lava Library would produce the best results for pulsed sphere comparisons with experiment data and other codes. That capability is nearly ready, and could be tested in the near future. The Mercury input files could be modified to more closely resemble the simulations in MCNP and Shift. In particular, a volumetric detector could be used to tally the transport particles instead of using the diagnostic ray trace detector for time dependent results that parallel how Shift is recording the tallies. Other benchmark problems could also be selected to test other coding features. For example, the pulsed spheres are a relatively small experiment, so it would be of interest to CEMeNT to test a benchmark that demands more computational power.

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